

Comparative Analysis And Enrichment Of The Nutrient Composition Of Fruit, Vegetable And Agro Waste By Composting With Earthworm *Eudilus Eugineae*, *Eisenia Fetida* And Millipede *Arthrosphaera Magna*

Rajkumar. G

Assistant Professor, PG and Research Department of Zoology, Yadava College, Madurai-625014

Corresponding Author- Rajkumar. G

Email- rajrgkumar@gmail.com

Abstract

India generates about 350 million tonnes of organic wastes every year. Vermicomposting and Millicomposting is a good and affordable technique used to produce organic compost from organic waste with the aid of specific earthworm and millipede species. It is one of the economically and environmentally friendly methods of organic waste processing. It is a newly becoming organic solid waste management strategies. The present research work was carried with the objective exploring the vermicomposting and millicomposting processing. In this experiment, the fruit waste, vegetable waste and agri residues was processed by two earthworm species, *Eudilus eugineae*, *Eisenia fetida* and one millipede species *Arthrosphaera magna*. The macronutrients such as carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and calcium were evaluated in vermicompost, millicompost and conventional compost and assessed the growth efficiency of plant, *Abelmoschus esculentus*. The nutrient status and growth efficiency of vermicompost and millicompost processed by earthworm species and millipede species produced from above said organic waste were more than conventional compost. Moreover, the biocompost produced together by *Eudilus eugineae*, *E.fetida* and *A.magna* processed higher nutrients and growth efficiency than that of other biocomposts. This study promising that biocomposting is an ecofriendly method to solve the acute problem of solid waste.

Key words: Fruit, Vegetable and Agro wastes, *Eudilus eugineae*, *Eisenia fetida*, *Athropsphaera magna* and *Abelmoschus esculentus*.

1. Introduction

Urbanization not only accumulates waste, but also accelerates generation rates of wastes. India will probably see a rise in waste generation from less than 40,000 metric tones per year to over 125,000 metric tones by the year 2030 (UNEP, 2003). The vegetable and fruit wastes from the markets, hotels, kitchen, fruit stalls and juice corners in the cities create pollution problems besides causing inconvenience to the public. Kale and Krishnamoorthy (1981) reported that the vegetable residues are the reserves of pathogens to cause epidemic diseases.

1. Compaction and destruction of soil structure
2. Poor water holding capacity of soil
3. Fertilizers are soil pollutants if it is in excess
4. Increased hazards and outbreak of pests, diseases and weeds

All these problems forced us to think about the alternative means. In this situation organic manures such as farm yard manure, compost, vermicompost, biofertilizer can be used at least complement if not as a substitute (Chackraborti and Singh, 2004). In recent years researchers have become progressively interested in using biological process for stabilizing organic wastes, which does not include a thermophilic stage, but involves the use of earthworms and millipedes for breaking down and stabilizing the organic wastes (Atiyeh et al., 2000).

Bio composting is an environmentally sound technology (EST) according criteria defined by the United Nations Environmental Program

(UNEP). They defined an EST as being less polluting, using resources in sustainable manner, recycling more of their wastes and products and handling all residual wastes in an environmentally acceptable way (Sharma and Agarwal, 2004). Jeevan Rao (1998) worked on the solid wastes and opined that the resource can be recycled and composting. The composting technique will help to reduce the solid waste and converts it into usable resource (Hosetti, 1998). Vermicomposting is an ecofriendly technique involving no pollution and hence is most suitable method for organic waste disposal when compared to the conventional methods like land filling, incineration, biogas production etc. Vermicomposting is the application of earthworm in producing vermifertilizer which helps in maintenance of better environment and results in sustainable agriculture (Senapati, 1996).

Similarly, Millipedes are known to be macro detritivorous terrestrial arthropods feed on decaying vegetable matter and mineral soil and represented by more than 8,000 species. They are essentially soil animals and in some ecosystem they are more important than worms as agents of soil and nutrient turn over.

In the light of information presented above, the present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To utilize the earthworm species, *Eisenia foetida*, *Eudrilus eugeniae* and millipede, *Arthrosphaera magna* to recycle the fruit, vegetable and agricultural wastes.

2. To analyze and compare the bio-chemical characteristics of the composts processed by earthworms and millipedes
3. To assess the effects of composts of different organic wastes on the growth of the vegetable plant, *Abelmoschus esculentus*

2. Materials And Methods

2.1 Collection of compost materials:

The fruit wastes like orange peels, skin and other parts of pine apple, grapes, papaya were collected from different Juice corners in and around Madurai. The vegetable wastes were obtained from the kitchen yard of Yadava College hostel. The predominant vegetable wastes are cabbage leaves, potato peels and over ripened tomatoes. Agricultural wastes like sugarcane trash, hay, and ground nut shells were collected from the nearby agricultural field and were separated, shredded to a length of 2-3 cm pieces, dried for a week and then subjected to pre decomposition.

2.2 Pre digestion of compost materials:

All these wastes were mixed with equal amount of fresh cow dung in plastic troughs separately and allowed for predigestion by sprinkling water. After 45 days, the predigested substrates were subjected to vermi / milli composting.

2.3 Collection and maintenance of compost organisms:

The most suitable earthworm species, *Eudrilus eugeniae*, *Eisenia foetida* and the detritivorous millipede, *Arthrosphaera magna* were chosen for the present investigation. Earthworms and millipedes were collected from SACS vermiery, Madurai and from the nearby Algar Hills garden soil respectively.

2.4 Biology of composting organisms:

2.4.1 Earthworms

The earthworm, *E. eugeniae* belongs to class Oligochaeta, order Haplotaxida and family Eudrilidae. It is commonly known as African worm or Night crawlers. It is a large composting worm, less tolerant to cold temperatures and best suited to tropical conditions (Edward et al., 1996). It is usually grown in temperature controlled conditions. It is epigeic i.e, lives on the surface of the soil or in the top 10 inches from the surface or on the topsoil under the litter layers

Eisenia foetida belongs to class Oligochaeta, order Haplotaxida and family Lumbricidae. It is popularly known as European worm. It is also epigeic, can tolerate at wide temperatures. *E. foetida* is commonly found in compost heaps, forests, gardens, under stones, logs and roadside dumps. Since *E. foetida* is found very close to human habitation, it has been used for home composting and fish bait

2.4.2 Millipedes:

Arthrosphaera magna : belongs to order Sphaerotheriida and family Sphaerotheriidae. Adults have exactly 13 segments (including collum and anal segments), and the juveniles are of dark olive colour. The head of the adult is yellow brown or olive brown or olive green, the second segment is dark brown with a black band bordered with yellow colour, forming a narrow stripe. The average weight, length and width of an adult millipede range from 4.5 to 12.5g, from 3.5 to 6.5, and from 1.5 to 2.5cm, respectively, Alagesan et al., 2013.

2.5 'Vermi' and 'Milli' bed preparation :

About 2.5 kg from the predigested materials of vegetable, fruit and agriculture wastes in moist condition were taken in separate 15 (5 troughs for each waste) rectangular culture troughs of equal size (47 x 32 x 16 cm). Among the 5 troughs, first one is without the composting organism, second, third, fourth with *E. foetida*, *E. eugeniae*, *Arthrosphaera magna* respectively, and the fifth with combination of the above two species of earthworms and a millipede species. Thirty earthworm species of *E. foetida* and *E. eugeniae* and millipede, *Arthrosphaera magna* were introduced separately in the second, third and fourth troughs respectively. In the fifth trough, 10 animals of each species of *E. foetida*, *E. eugeniae* and *Arthrosphaera magna* were introduced. Water was sprinkled with regular intervals in all the troughs to maintain moisture content of 65 – 75% RH and a temperature at 25° C. The troughs were covered with wet muslin cloth to prevent the invasion of foreign materials and outgoing of millipedes. The bio composting process was extended for a period of 60 days. The biodegradation of wastes without the experimental organisms is referred as 'Compost'. The compost prepared by the action of earthworms and millipedes is named as 'Vermicompost' and 'Milli'compost respectively. Spraying of water was stopped two days before the harvest.

Before introducing the earthworms and millipedes into the troughs i.e. at the initial (0 day) and after an interval of 20, 40 and 60th days, the samples of compost, vermicompost and millicompost were analyzed for the biochemical composition of Organic carbon, Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Calcium and Potassium.

2.6 Bio Chemical Estimation

2.6.1 Estimation of Organic carbon:

The organic carbon was estimated following in the method of Walkey and Black method in Jackson (1974). 0.1g of sample was placed in 250ml standard flask. To this 10ml of potassium dichromate was added. The contents were mixed by gently swirling the flask. Now 20ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added and mixed well. It was kept for 20 to 30minutes.

Simultaneously a blank was prepared. The solution was diluted to 200ml with distilled water and 10ml of Orthophosphoric acid and a few drops of Diphenylamine indicator were added. The solution was titrated against 0.5N ferrous ammonium sulphate taken in a burette. The colour change from dull green to turbid blue and the end point, the sudden appearance of brilliant green was noted. The amount of organic carbon present in the samples was estimated and expressed in percentage.

2.6.2 Estimation of total Nitrogen:

The nitrogen content was determined by the modified Micro-Kjeldhal method (Umbreit et.al, 1974). The catalyst was prepared by powdering and mixing copper sulphate (1g), potassium sulphate (8g) and selenium dioxide (1g). Potassium iodide (4g) and mercuric iodide (4g) were dissolved in 25ml of distilled water. About 1.75g of Gum Arabic was powdered and dissolved in 750ml of boiling water. Then potassium iodide- mercuric iodide solution was mixed with Gum Arabic solution. This solution was made up to 1000ml with distilled water and then filtered through Wattmann No.1 filter paper. Ten mg of powdered sample was taken in a Micro-Kjeldhal flask. A pinch of catalyst and 0.5ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was introduced into the Kjeldhal flask. The flask was gently heated in a digestion rack until fumes of sulphuric acid entered. It was then strongly heated until the digest in the flask turned into an apple green colour. After cooling, the digest was made up to 20ml with distilled water. To 1ml of the diluted digest 2ml of water, 2ml of colour reagent and 3ml of 2N NaOH were added. After 15minutes the absorbance of the solution was read at 490nm against reagent blank in a spectrophotometer. The quantity of nitrogen in the sample was determined with reference to a standard graph prepared using NH_4Cl and expressed as percentage.

2.6.3 Estimation of phosphorous:

The phosphorous estimation was followed by modified Vogels method, (1963). 100mg sample was dissolved in 100ml of distilled water. From this 5ml was taken in a 50ml volumetric flask and 2ml of ammonium molybdate mixture was added. A few drops of stannous chloride or stannous oxalate were added. Light blue colour appeared. The optical density of the developed light blue colour was read at 640nm in a colorimeter. The amount of phosphorous in the sample was calculated and expressed in percentage

2.6.4 Estimation of potassium and calcium:

The amount of potassium and calcium present in the samples was estimated with the help of Flame photometry (Model CL – 22D).

2.6.4.1 Estimation of potassium

Preparation of reagents: 1.909gm AR potassium chloride was taken in a 1litre volumetric

flask and made up the solution to the mark with double distilled water. Different concentrations (100, 50, 20, 10, 5, and 2ppm) were prepared from the stock solutions.

2.6.4.2 Estimation of calcium

Preparation of reagents: 0.1248g of AR grade calcium carbonate was taken and dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid. It was transferred volumetric flask and made up to the mark with double distilled water. This stock standard solution contained 100ppm of calcium. The solution was diluted to 50, 20, 10, 5ppm of calcium.

100mg of sample was dissolved in 10ml of 1N Hydrochloric acid and made up to 100ml with distilled water. This solution centrifuged at 1000rpm for 10minutes and filtered. First the filter is set, the compressor is started and the burner of the Flame photometer is lighted. The air pressure is adjusted for the gas feeder to have a sharp blue flame. The potassium / calcium solution of the highest value is fed in the range and the flame photometer is adjusted. To read full value of emission on the scale, distilled water is fed and the flame photometer is adjusted to read zero. Now the sample filtrate is fed and the Galvanometer reading for potassium and calcium was noted. The result obtained in ppm was converted into percentage.

2.7 Pot experiment:

To assess the fertility of the different composts processed by earthworms and millipedes, the vegetable plant, *Abelmoschus esculentus* was selected. About 2 kg of composts (conventional), vermi and 'milli' composts were taken in separate pots and in each pot 10 seeds of *A. esculentus* were sowed and maintained for a period of 45 days. The data related to morphometry and bionomics of the plant was observed and recorded.

2.8 Statistical application:

Wherever required the data were subjected to statistical analysis, like Standard Deviation (S.D) and Pearson's product moment Correlation coefficient ('r').

3. Results

Data related to the chemical composition of the compost produced from the fruit, vegetable and agricultural wastes by the activity of the earthworms, *E. eugeniae*, *E. foetida* and millipede, *Arthrosphaera magna* are presented in Tables 1- 12.

3.1 Organic carbon:

The carbon content of the fruit waste compost was decreased from 36.27 to 29.54 27.52 and 26.15% at the end of 60th day processed by *Arthrosphaera magna*, *E. foetida* and *E. eugeniae* respectively. Maximum decline in the organic carbon content was observed (24.22%) in the compost prepared by the combined activity of millipede, *Arthrosphaera magna* and earthworms, *E. foetida* and *E. eugeniae* (Table 4). Similarly, the

percentage of carbon was declined from the initial day (42.01%) to the final day of composting in vegetable compost processed by *Arthrospira magna* (33.22%), *E. foetida* (31.19%), *E. eugeniae* (30.19%) and the combination of millipedes and earthworms (28.11%). Though the unprocessed agriculture wastes contain high carbon content (46.28%), it was tremendously decreased (33.21%) at the end of 60th day by the combined action of *E. eugeniae*, *E. foetida* and (Fig.1). *Arthrospira magna* Analysis of correlation coefficient showed that a significant negative correlation (< 0.05) was obtained between different day composts of tested wastes and the organic carbon (Table 13).

3.2 Nitrogen:

The agricultural wastes contained significantly less nitrogen (0.83%) than fruit (0.86%) and vegetable wastes (0.96%) at the initial stage of composting. But at the end of 60th day, the compost prepared from the agricultural wastes by the integrated activity of species of earthworms *E. eugeniae*, *E. foetida* and millipede, *Arthrospira magna* showed maximum nitrogen content (1.32%) compared to vegetable (1.21%) and fruit wastes (0.96%). Minimum amount of nitrogen was noticed in the fruit waste (0.91%) composted by the millipede, *Arthrospira magna* at the end of experiment. Among the two earthworm species, *E. eugeniae* was very efficient in increasing the nitrogen content from 0.83 to 1.21% compared to *E. foetida* (1.10%) in composted agricultural wastes. Statistically significant positive correlation was obtained for the different duration of the organic wastes and the nitrogen content (Table 13).

3.3 C/N ratio:

The C/N ratio was maximum (55.75) in agricultural waste and it was found to be less in vegetable (43.76) and fruit (42.17) wastes at the initial stage. But the C/N ratio was remarkably decreased to 23.23, 25.15 and 25.22 by the efficient converting mechanisms and the coexisting adaptability of *E. eugeniae*, *E. foetida* and *Arthrospira magna* in vegetable, agricultural and fruit wastes respectively. Of these three species, *E. eugeniae* is very potent in reducing the C/N ratio compared to *E. foetida* and in all the *Arthrospira magna* tested wastes. Statistical analysis showed that a significant negative correlation was obtained between the duration of composting and different wastes processed by earthworms and millipedes ('r' values: -0.9959, -0.9951, -0.9961, -0.9957 for agricultural wastes; -0.9954, -0.9979, -0.9894, -0.9842 for fruit wastes; -0.9922, -0.9151, -0.9996, -0.9966 for vegetable composts produced by *E. eugeniae*, *E. foetida*, *Arthrospira magna* and combination of all these three species) (Table 13).

3.4 Phosphorus:

The level of phosphorus at the commencement of composting was 0.23, 0.37 and 0.21% in fruit, vegetable and agricultural wastes respectively. After 60 days, the compost without earthworms and millipedes contained less amount of phosphorus (0.35, 0.49 and 0.37%) than the composts obtained by the combined activity *E. eugeniae*, *E. foetida* and *Arthrospira magna* (0.47, 0.69 and 0.42%) in fruit, vegetable and agricultural wastes respectively. The earthworm species, *E. eugeniae* was found to be very effective in increasing the phosphorus content during the process of composting of different substrates compared to *E. foetida* and *Arthrospira magna*. The relationship between the phosphorus content and the different day substrates are statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

3.5 Potassium:

The potassium content of the substrates used for composting was increased in the order of agricultural (0.32%), fruit (0.45%) and vegetable wastes (0.66%) at the beginning of the composting. The vegetable wastes composted by *E. eugeniae* contained more potassium (0.98%) than fruit (0.74%) and agriculture wastes (0.69%). The earthworm, *E. foetida* was also very effective in increasing the content of potassium in the compost (0.61, 0.68 and 0.92%) compared to the millipede, *Arthrospira magna* (0.58, 0.59 and 0.85%) in agricultural, fruit and vegetable wastes respectively. Similarly, maximum increase in the quantity of potassium (1.25%) was noticed when the vegetable wastes were degraded by the combined action of treated with earthworms and millipedes.

3.6 Calcium:

The initial level of calcium content was reported as 0.43, 0.52 and 0.85% in agricultural, fruit and vegetable wastes respectively. After treating with earthworms and millipedes separately and combination of both, the calcium content was remarkably increased. *E. eugeniae* increased the calcium level from 0.85 to 1.14% in vegetable wastes after 60 days of composting. The amount of calcium increase was found to be very less i.e from 0.52 to 0.62% in fruit waste processed by the millipede, *Arthrospira magna*. However, a remarkable increase in the level of calcium was observed in the composted vegetable (1.82%) compared to fruit (0.92%) and agricultural wastes (0.83%) processed by the combination of earthworms and millipedes. Statistically significant positive correlation was obtained for the different duration of the organic wastes and the calcium content (Table 13).

3.7 Pot experiment:

Data related to the effect of different composts obtained from the activity earthworms and

millipedes on the growth parameters of the vegetable plant, *Abelmoschus esculentus* was presented in Tables 14- 16. The results revealed that the plants grown on vegetable wastes attained maximum height (38.6 cm) compared to fruit (34.8 cm) and agricultural wastes (30.5 cm) processed by the combination of earthworms and millipedes. Similarly, the other parameters including number

and length of leaves; length and weight of fruits were greater in vegetable wastes than the fruit and agricultural wastes. Interestingly, the plant grown on vegetable wastes composted with *E. eugeniae* attained maximum height (34.4 cm), length (21.7cm) and number of leaf (12.7/ plant), fruit length (14.9 cm) and weight (16.4gm) than the wastes worked with other earthworm species

Table 1: Nutrient composition (%) of vermicompost of fruit wastes processed by *E.euginae*. Each value represents the mean of ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost
Organic Carbon	36.27 ± 1.81	34.26 ± 1.02	33.58 ± 2.68	31.93 ± 2.55	30.57 ± 1.22	28.91 ± 0.86	26.15 ± 1.56
Nitrogen	0.86 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.05	0.89 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.05	0.92 ± 0.05	0.95 ± 0.02
Phosphorus	0.23 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.01	0.28 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.01	0.32 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.01
Potassium	0.45 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.02	0.52 ± 0.04	0.52 ± 0.04	0.63 ± 0.03	0.60 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.04
Calcium	0.52 ± 0.01	0.56 ± 0.02	0.64 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.03	0.75 ± 0.04	0.72 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.04
C/N Ratio	42.17 ± 1.26	39.37 ± 1.96	38.15 ± 2.28	35.87 ± 1.79	33.59 ± 1.00	31.42 ± 1.25	27.52 ± 1.37

Table 2: Nutrient composition (%) of vermicompost of fruit wastes processed by *E. foetida*. Each value represents the mean of ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost
Organic Carbon	36.27 ± 2.17	34.27 ± 1.71	33.25 ± 1.66	32.93 ± 1.97	30.97 ± 1.85	29.91 ± 1.19	27.52 ± 1.37
Nitrogen	0.86 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.05	0.88 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.06	0.90 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.04	0.93 ± 0.02
Phosphorus	0.23 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.02	0.30 ± 0.02	0.33 ± 0.01	0.32 ± 0.01	0.39 ± 0.03
Potassium	0.45 ± 0.01	0.48 ± 0.02	0.52 ± 0.04	0.51 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.01	0.54 ± 0.03	0.68 ± 0.05
Calcium	0.52 ± 0.01	0.55 ± 0.04	0.57 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.05	0.63 ± 0.02	0.63 ± 0.03	0.77 ± 0.03
C/N Ratio	42.17 ± 2.53	39.39 ± 1.57	37.78 ± 1.88	37.42 ± 1.87	34.41 ± 1.37	33.23 ± 2.65	29.59 ± 1.47

Table 3: Nutrient composition (%) of 'Milli'compost of fruit wastes processed by *A. magna* Each value represents the mean of ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	'Milli' compost	Compost	'Milli' compost	Compost	'Milli' compost
Organic Carbon	36.27 ± 1.81	35.26 ± 1.41	34.92 ± 1.04	33.93 ± 1.69	32.58 ± 1.62	30.91 ± 1.23	29.54 ± 1.18
Nitrogen	0.86 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.03	0.87 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.04	0.89 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.05
Phosphorus	0.23 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.01	0.27 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.02	0.31 ± 0.01	0.30 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.02
Potassium	0.45 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.01	0.48 ± 0.03	0.49 ± 0.02	0.52 ± 0.04	0.52 ± 0.03	0.59 ± 0.02
Calcium	0.52 ± 0.03	0.54 ± 0.03	0.54 ± 0.02	0.56 ± 0.04	0.57 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.02	0.62 ± 0.04
C/N Ratio	42.17 ± 3.37	41.00 ± 2.87	40.13 ± 2.40	38.55 ± 1.92	36.60 ± 1.46	34.73 ± 1.04	32.46 ± 0.97

Table 4: Nutrient composition (%) of compost and earthworm millipede compost of fruit wastes processed by *E. euginae*, *E. foetida* and *A.magna* . Each value represents the mean of ($X \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost
Organic Carbon	36.27 ± 1.08	35.26 ± 1.76	34.58 ± 1.72	32.93 ± 1.31	29.55 ± 1.47	30.91 ± 1.54	24.22 ± 1.21
Nitrogen	0.86 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.05	0.88 ± 0.03	0.91 ± 0.05	0.90 ± 0.05	0.96 ± 0.03
Phosphorus	0.23 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.02	0.30 ± 0.02	0.39 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.03
Potassium	0.45 ± 0.02	0.50 ± 0.02	0.54 ± 0.02	0.56 ± 0.03	0.69 ± 0.04	0.62 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.05
Calcium	0.52 ± 0.01	0.57 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.03	0.66 ± 0.03	0.77 ± 0.04	0.75 ± 0.06	0.92 ± 0.04
C/N Ratio	42.17 ± 2.95	40.52 ± 2.43	39.29 ± 1.96	37.42 ± 2.99	32.47 ± 1.62	34.34 ± 1.71	25.22 ± 1.26

Table 5: Nutrient composition (%) of vermicompost of vegetable wastes processed by *E.euginae*. Each value represents the mean of ($X \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost
Organic Carbon	42.01 ± 2.10	40.92 ± 1.63	39.24 ± 1.96	37.58 ± 1.50	35.57 ± 1.77	34.92 ± 1.39	30.19 ± 1.20
Nitrogen	0.96 ± 0.03	0.97 ± 0.04	0.98 ± 0.04	1.02 ± 0.04	1.04 ± 0.06	1.04 ± 0.06	1.10 ± 0.05
Phosphorus	0.37 ± 0.01	0.39 ± 0.01	0.43 ± 0.02	0.42 ± 0.01	0.52 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.05
Potassium	0.66 ± 0.01	0.69 ± 0.03	0.72 ± 0.04	0.73 ± 0.03	0.84 ± 0.03	0.78 ± 0.04	0.98 ± 0.03
Calcium	0.85 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.03	0.96 ± 0.04	1.12 ± 0.05	1.10 ± 0.06	1.44 ± 0.04
C/N Ratio	43.76 ± 2.18	42.18 ± 2.53	40.04 ± 2.00	36.84 ± 1.84	34.20 ± 2.05	33.57 ± 2.01	27.44 ± 1.64

Table 6: Nutrient composition (%) of vermicompost of vegetable wastes processed by *E. foetida*. Each value represents the mean of ($X \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost
Organic Carbon	42.01 ± 1.26	40.92 ± 1.63	39.59 ± 1.58	38.58 ± 2.31	35.23 ± 1.40	35.92 ± 1.79	31.19 ± 1.24
Nitrogen	0.96 ± 0.04	0.98 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.03	1.00 ± 0.05	1.03 ± 0.03	1.02 ± 0.04	1.06 ± 0.06
Phosphorus	0.37 ± 0.01	0.39 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.01	0.47 ± 0.02	0.45 ± 0.01	0.52 ± 0.02
Potassium	0.66 ± 0.02	0.70 ± 0.02	0.72 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.03	0.79 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.05
Calcium	0.85 ± 0.03	0.89 ± 0.04	0.92 ± 0.04	0.94 ± 0.05	1.13 ± 0.05	1.06 ± 0.03	1.32 ± 0.05
C/N Ratio	43.76 ± 2.18	41.75 ± 1.67	39.98 ± 1.19	38.58 ± 1.54	34.20 ± 1.72	35.21 ± 2.11	29.42 ± 1.17

Table 7: Nutrient composition (%) of ‘Milli’compost of vegetable wastes processed by A.magna. Each value represents the mean of (X ± S.D) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	‘Milli’ compost	Compost	‘Milli’ compost	Compost	‘Milli’ compost
Organic Carbon	42.01 ± 2.10	41.14 ± 2.46	39.27 ± 1.98	38.58 ± 1.54	36.56 ± 1.82	35.92 ± 2.15	33.22 ± 1.66
Nitrogen	0.96 ± 0.04	0.97 ± 0.04	0.98 ± 0.05	0.97 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.04	0.98 ± 0.05	0.99 ± 0.03
Phosphorus	0.37 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.01	0.39 ± 0.02	0.39 ± 0.01	0.41 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.02	0.43 ± 0.02
Potassium	0.66 ± 0.01	0.70 ± 0.03	0.72 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.03	0.79 ± 0.04	0.80 ± 0.05	0.85 ± 0.05
Calcium	0.85 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.05	0.94 ± 0.03	1.07 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.07	1.20 ± 0.06
C/N Ratio	43.76 ± 1.31	42.41 ± 1.69	40.07 ± 2.00	39.77 ± 2.38	36.92 ± 2.58	36.65 ± 1.83	33.55 ± 1.67

Table 8: Nutrient composition (%) of vermi and ‘Milli’compost of vegetable wastes processed by E. euginae, E. foetida and A.magna. Each value represents the mean of (X ± S.D) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi-‘Milli’ compost	Compost	Vermi-‘Milli’ compost	Compost	Vermi-‘Milli’ compost
Organic Carbon	42.01 ± 2.10	39.92 ± 1.19	38.92 ± 1.55	37.58 ± 1.87	33.23 ± 0.99	32.42 ± 1.94	28.11 ± 0.84
Nitrogen	0.96 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.03	1.02 ± 0.04	1.00 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.05	1.12 ± 0.04	1.21 ± 0.07
Phosphorus	0.37 ± 0.01	0.39 ± 0.01	0.46 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.01	0.58 ± 0.03	0.49 ± 0.02	0.69 ± 0.04
Potassium	0.66 ± 0.03	0.72 ± 0.03	0.82 ± 0.04	0.86 ± 0.02	1.12 ± 0.05	0.97 ± 0.03	1.25 ± 0.07
Calcium	0.85 ± 0.05	1.02 ± 0.05	1.21 ± 0.03	1.18 ± 0.04	1.52 ± 0.07	1.34 ± 0.06	1.82 ± 0.09
C/N Ratio	43.76 ± 2.18	40.73 ± 1.22	38.15 ± 1.90	37.58 ± 1.87	29.40 ± 1.17	28.94 ± 1.73	23.23 ± 1.16

Table 9: Nutrient composition (%) of vermicompost of Agro wastes processed by E.euginae. Each value represents the mean of (X ± S.D) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost
Organic Carbon	46.28 ± 1.38	45.26 ± 2.26	43.25 ± 1.72	43.26 ± 2.59	39.23 ± 1.56	40.90 ± 2.04	34.24 ± 2.04
Nitrogen	0.83 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.04	0.92 ± 0.03	0.91 ± 0.04	1.11 ± 0.06	0.98 ± 0.04	1.21 ± 0.06
Phosphorus	0.21 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.01	0.23 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.02
Potassium	0.32 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.01	0.39 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.03	0.42 ± 0.02	0.69 ± 0.02
Calcium	0.43 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.02	0.51 ± 0.03	0.49 ± 0.03	0.64 ± 0.03	0.51 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.03
C/N Ratio	55.75 ± 2.78	53.24 ± 3.19	47.01 ± 2.35	47.53 ± 2.85	35.34 ± 2.12	41.73 ± 2.08	28.30 ± 1.43

Table 10: Nutrient composition (%) of vermicompost of Agro wastes processed by *E. foetida*. Each value represents the mean of ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost	Compost	Vermi compost
Organic Carbon	46.28 ± 2.31	44.81 ± 1.79	43.74 ± 2.18	42.53 ± 2.12	38.21 ± 2.29	39.9 ± 1.59	35.81 ± 1.43
Nitrogen	0.83 ± 0.02	0.84 ± 0.04	0.90 ± 0.03	0.89 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.05	0.94 ± 0.05	1.10 ± 0.06
Phosphorus	0.21 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.01	0.27 ± 0.01	0.33 ± 0.01
Potassium	0.32 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.01	0.51 ± 0.04	0.41 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.03
Calcium	0.43 ± 0.02	0.45 ± 0.02	0.49 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.01	0.52 ± 0.02	0.70 ± 0.04
C/N Ratio	55.75 ± 1.67	53.34 ± 1.60	48.60 ± 2.43	47.78 ± 2.86	38.59 ± 2.31	42.44 ± 2.12	32.56 ± 1.30

Table 11: Nutrient composition (%) of 'Milli'compost of Agro wastes processed by *A.magna*. Each value represents the mean of ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	'Milli' compost	Compost	'Milli' compost	Compost	'Milli' compost
Organic Carbon	46.28 ± 1.38	45.34 ± 1.81	44.75 ± 1.79	43.26 ± 2.16	41.22 ± 2.47	40.90 ± 2.45	38.12 ± 1.90
Nitrogen	0.83 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.04	0.89 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.05
Phosphorus	0.21 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.01	0.23 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.02	0.26 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.02
Potassium	0.32 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.02	0.45 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.03
Calcium	0.43 ± 0.01	0.44 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.01	0.47 ± 0.02	0.52 ± 0.04	0.51 ± 0.04	0.67 ± 0.02
C/N Ratio	55.75 ± 2.78	53.34 ± 3.20	51.43 ± 2.05	48.60 ± 1.45	44.80 ± 1.79	43.97 ± 3.07	38.50 ± 1.54

Table 12: Nutrient composition (%) of vermi and 'Milli'compost of vegetable wastes processed by *E. euginae*, *E. foetida* and *A.magna*. Each value represents the mean of ($\bar{X} \pm S.D$) of 3 estimates

Parameters	Initial (0 day)	20 th day		40 th day		60 th day	
		Compost	Vermi- 'Milli' compost	Compost	Vermi- 'Milli' compost	Compost	Vermi- 'Milli' compost
Organic Carbon	46.28 ± 1.85	44.26 ± 2.65	42.58 ± 2.12	42.16 ± 2.10	38.27 ± 1.53	39.12 ± 2.34	33.21 ± 1.32
Nitrogen	0.83 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.04	0.93 ± 0.03	1.17 ± 0.05	0.99 ± 0.02	1.32 ± 0.03
Phosphorus	0.21 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.01	0.31 ± 0.01	0.33 ± 0.02	0.37 ± 0.02	0.42 ± 0.02
Potassium	0.32 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.02	0.75 ± 0.04
Calcium	0.43 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.01	0.55 ± 0.03	0.52 ± 0.03	0.69 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.03	0.83 ± 0.03
C/N Ratio	55.75 ± 1.67	50.87 ± 2.03	45.29 ± 1.81	45.33 ± 2.26	32.70 ± 1.63	39.51 ± 2.37	25.15 ± 1.25

Table 13: Correlation coefficient (r) relating the biochemical parameters and the composts of different wastes processed by earthworms and millipedes

Fruit wastes				
Parameters	E. eugeniae	E. foetida	A.magna	Ee + Ef + Am
Organic carbon	-0.9928	-0.9972	-0.9861	-0.9785
Nitrogen	0.9829	0.9944	0.9898	0.9795
Phosphorus	0.9852	0.9886	0.9999	0.9999
Potassium	0.9951	0.9979	0.9807	0.9999
Calcium	0.9995	0.9671	0.9795	0.9935
C/N ratio	-0.9954	-0.9979	-0.9894	-0.9842
Vegetable wastes				
Organic carbon	-0.9889	-0.9933	-0.9987	-0.9932
Nitrogen	0.9798	0.9983	0.9129	0.9944
Phosphorus	0.9965	0.9999	0.9999	0.9985
Potassium	0.9859	0.9918	0.9985	0.9885
Calcium	0.9666	0.9819	0.9983	0.9991
C/N ratio	-0.9922	-0.9151	-0.9996	-0.9966
Agricultural wastes				
Organic carbon	-0.9941	-0.9865	-0.9885	-0.9976
Nitrogen	0.9898	0.9951	0.9898	0.9918
Phosphorus	0.9929	0.9958	0.9959	0.9919
Potassium	0.9645	0.9911	0.9788	0.9923
Calcium	0.9931	0.9921	0.6431	0.9993
C/N ratio	-0.9959	-0.9951	-0.9961	-0.9957

Table 14: Effect of fruit wastes composted with earthworms and millipedes on the bionomics of *Abelmoschus esculentus*. Each value represents as mean (X ± S.D) of 5 observations

Parameters	Conventional Compost	Composted with			
		E. eugeniae	E. foetida	A.magna	Ee+Ef+Xc
Height of plant (cm)	21.5 ± 1.88	33.3 ± 2.28	30.0 ± 2.24	28.0 ± 1.81	34.8 ± 2.21
No. of leaves	7.4 ± 0.52	11.5 ± 0.79	10.5 ± 0.51	9.4 ± 0.47	14.2 ± 1.12
Leaf length (cm)	13.7 ± 0.73	18.5 ± 1.78	17.3 ± 1.42	15.8 ± 0.97	20.1 ± 1.75
Fruit length (cm)	9.5 ± 0.45	14.4 ± 1.12	13.2 ± 0.92	11.5 ± 0.91	15.3 ± 1.32
Fruit weight (gm)	11.6 ± 0.61	15.2 ± 1.39	14.1 ± 1.02	13.4 ± 0.98	16.5 ± 1.12

Table 15: Effect of vegetable wastes composted with earthworms and millipedes on the bionomics of *Abelmoschus esculentus*. Each value represents as mean (X ± S.D) of 5 observations

Parameters	Conventional Compost	Composted with			
		E. eugeniae	E. foetida	A.magna	Ee+Ef+Xc
Height of plant (cm)	20.1 ± 1.45	34.4 ± 2.15	32.0 ± 2.46	30.0 ± 1.96	38.6 ± 2.21
No. of leaves	8.9 ± 0.41	12.7 ± 0.88	12.2 ± 0.91	10.5 ± 0.64	15.7 ± 1.12
Leaf length (cm)	15.3 ± 1.01	21.7 ± 1.96	20.3 ± 1.75	18.9 ± 1.2	22.9 ± 1.89
Fruit length (cm)	9.1 ± 0.52	14.9 ± 1.21	13.8 ± 1.01	12.5 ± 1.13	15.9 ± 1.25
Fruit weight (gm)	11.9 ± 0.98	16.4 ± 1.22	15.2 ± 1.14	13.7 ± 1.08	18.9 ± 1.51

Table 16: Effect of agricultural wastes composted with earthworms and millipedes on the bionomics of *Abelmoschus esculentus*. Each value represents as mean ($X \pm S.D$) of 5 observations

Parameters	Conventional Compost	Composted with			
		<i>E. eugeniae</i>	<i>E. foetida</i>	<i>A. magna</i>	Ee+Ef+Xc
Height of plant (cm)	19.1 ± 1.12	29.5 ± 2.18	27.2 ± 2.01	25.0 ± 2.0	30.5 ± 2.75
No. of leaves	6.9 ± 0.32	10.7 ± 0.54	9.3 ± 0.46	8.7 ± 0.38	12.9 ± 0.65
Leaf length (cm)	10.3 ± 0.58	16.6 ± 0.88	15.5 ± 0.75	13.2 ± 0.62	18.7 ± 0.99
Fruit length (cm)	10.4 ± 0.99	14.0 ± 1.02	13.0 ± 0.99	10.2 ± 0.78	14.8 ± 0.97
Fruit weight (gm)	9.1 ± 0.49	14.3 ± 0.99	13.2 ± 0.89	10.5 ± 0.79	15.9 ± 0.95

5. Discussion

The results obtained from the present investigation revealed that the compost and composts prepared from different organic waste materials processed by the earthworms, *E. eugeniae* and *E. foetida* and millipede, *Arthrosphaera magna* were highly potentials than the compost produced by conventional methods, in terms of nutritional quality and its influence on the growth of the vegetable plant, *Abelmoschus esculentus*. Ambarish and Sridhar, et al., 2015 reported increase in the concentration of N, P, K and Ca in compost produced with the help of millipede and earthworm.

7. References

1. **Alagesan, P., Ramanathan, B.**, 2013 Diversity of Millipedes in Alagar Hills Reserve Forest in Tamil Nadu, India, Hindawi Publishing corporation,. International Journal of Biodiversity Volume 2013, Article ID 715460 5 pages.
2. **Ambarish, C.N. and K.R. Sridhar, 2015.** Microbial dynamics in food, intestine and fecal pellets, of two endemic pill-millipedes (*Arthrosphaera*; *Sphaerotheriida*) of the western Ghats. International journal Agricultural Technology, 11(3); 637-648.
3. **Atiyeh, R., M. Subler, C.A. Edwards, G. Bachman, J.D. Metzger and W. Shuster** (2000) Effects of vermicomposts and composts on plant growth in horticultural container media and soil. J. Pedobiol. 44: pp 579- 590.
4. **Chakraborti, M and N.P. Singh** (2004) Bio-compost: A Novel input to the Organic Farming. Agrobios. Vol. 2, (8): 45-47
5. **Edwards, C. A. and P.J. Bohlen** (1996) Biology and Ecology of Earthworms. 3rd ed. Chapman and Hall, London. Pp 26-31.
6. **Hosetti, B. B** (1998) Solid waste management in India. General aspects. In: Environmental impact assessment and management (Eds.Hosetti, B. B. and Kumar, A) Daya publishing House. Delhi. pp132- 147.
7. **Jackson, M.L.** (1974) Soil chemical analysis. Prentice Hall of India(Pvt) Ltd., New Delhi, Pp-498
8. **Jeevan Rao. K.** (1998) Urban soild waste management with rerference to Hyderabad city. In: Environmental impact assessment and management (Ed. Hosetti, B.B. and Kumar, A) Daya publishing House , Delhi. pp148- 171.
9. **Kale, R. D. and R.V. Krishnanmoorthy** (1981) Enrichment of water soluble calcium and carbohydrates of soil by earthworm, *Pontoscolex corethrurus*, Soil Biol. and Biochem. pp88-91.
10. **Sharma, A., and A. K, Agarwal** (2004) Organic farming- Todays evolution, Tomorrows prosperity. J. Agrobios. 3: 16- 18.
11. **Senapathi, P. K** (1996) In proceeding "Recommendations of National Workshop on Organic Farming for Sustainable Agriculture". 187-189.
12. **Umbreit, W. W., R. N. Burris and J. F. Stauffer** (1974) Method for nitrogen estimation. In: Manometric and Biochemical Techniques. Minneasota: Burgess Publishing Company . 358p
13. **United Nations Environmental Program** (2003) - 'Urban waste management strategy, First Edition, Bulletin, Pp 1-10